

Synthesis, spectral characterization and redox properties of a hetero-tetranuclear biimidazolato-bridged complex with Os^{II}₂Ag^I₂ core

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Abstract : A hetero-tetranuclear complex of osmium(II) and silver(I) containing the terminal ligand 2-(phenylazo)pyridine (pap) and the bridging ligand 2,2'-biimidazolate (biim²⁻) has been synthesized. The complex is characterized by the analysis of physicochemical data. Electron spray ionization mass spectrum (ESIMS) of the complex has been reported which authenticates its formulation. The compound exhibits a strong MLCT band at 510 nm, the intensity of which is almost double than that observed for the corresponding monomeric building block. Cyclic voltammetric studies of the complex is reported. Multiple redox responses are observed at the negative of SCE which are assigned due to the reductions of coordinated pap ligands.

Keywords : Osmium silver biimidazolate, hetero-tetranuclear, synthesis, redox, 2-(phenylazo)pyridine.

Introduction

This work is in continuation of the interest in the synthesis of hetero-polynuclear redox active complexes¹ based on unusual binding mode of 2,2'-biimidazolate bridging ligand in the context of studies of electron transfer processes and metallophilic interactions². It may be noted that 2,2'-biimidazole (biimH₂) can act as an unusual bridge^{2a,3}, attached to three metal centres, only on complete deprotonation (**I** and **II**). The pK_a values of biimH₂ are high⁴ and for this reason, even coordinated M-biimH₂, in most cases, fails to act as a building unit for the construction of polynuclear compounds. However, it has been shown in our earlier work^{5a} that the presence of a strong π-acceptor ligand like pap can decrease the pK_a values of coordinated biimH₂, as in [Os(pap)₂biimH₂]²⁺, by a considerable extent (3.8 and 6.5) and in turn makes it a useful building unit for the synthesis of multinuclear systems.

Here, the synthesis, characterization and redox properties of a Os/Ag tetranuclear complex, obtained from the reaction of methanolic solution of [Os(pap)₂biimH₂]²⁺ with ammoniacal silver nitrate, is reported. It is to be noted here that earlier we have reported^{2a} a similar type

of Ru/Ag tetranuclear complex having argentophilic interactions.

Experimental

Materials :

The starting complex [Os(pap)₂biimH₂](ClO₄)₂·2H₂O was synthesized as reported earlier^{5a}. Silver nitrate was received from Merck, India. Solvents and other chemicals used for synthesis were of analytical grade. The supporting electrolyte (tetraethyl ammonium perchlorate, TEAP) and solvents for electrochemical work were obtained as described earlier⁶. CAUTION : perchlorate salts of metal complexes are generally explosive. Although no detonation tendencies have been observed, care is advised and handling of only small quantities recommended.

Physical measurements :

A Shimadzu UV 2100 UV-Vis Recording Spectrophotometer was used to record electronic spectra. IR spectrum was recorded with a Perkin-Elmer 783 IR spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectrum was measured in CDCl_3 with a Bruker Avance DPX 300 spectrophotometer and SiMe_4 as the internal standard. A Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer was used to collect microanalytical data (C, H, N). Electrochemical measurements were carried out under a dry nitrogen atmosphere on a PAR Model 370-4 Electrochemistry System as described earlier⁵. All potentials reported in this work are uncorrected for junction contribution. Electrical conductivity was measured by using a Systronics Direct Reading Conductivity Meter 304. ESIMS measurements were carried out by using a sector type mass spectrometer (JEOL-D300) connected with a home-made ESI interface as described earlier^{5b}.

Synthesis of the complex, $[\{\text{Os}(\text{pap})_2\text{biim}\}_2\text{Ag}_2]-(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$:

0.1 g (0.108 mmol) $[\text{Os}(\text{pap})_2\text{biimH}_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was dissolved in 25 ml of methanol. To this solution ammoniacal silver nitrate, containing 0.019 g (0.111 mmol) AgNO_3 , was added. The color of the solution changed from pink-brown to brown-violet. The solution was then stirred at room temperature for ~ 1 h using a magnetic stirrer. The solution was then filtered through a sintered-glass funnel and the filtrate was allowed to evaporate slowly at room temperature (in absence of light). The dark compound thus obtained was finally re-crystallized from acetonitrile-water solvent mixture, filtered and dried in vacuum. Yield : 60%. Anal Calcd. for $\text{C}_{56}\text{H}_{46}\text{N}_{20}\text{Cl}_2\text{O}_9\text{Ag}_2\text{Os}_2$: C, 37.14; H, 2.54; N, 15.47. Found : C, 37.27; H, 2.78; N, 15.18; $\Lambda_{\text{M}} = 180 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ ($1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ in MeOH).

Results and discussion*Synthesis :*

In earlier publications⁵ it was shown that in presence of a strong π -acid co-ligand 2-(phenylazo)pyridine (pap), the complex $[\text{Os}(\text{pap})_2\text{biimH}_2]^{2+}$ exhibits relatively low pK_{a} values (3.8 and 6.5) and upon complete deprotonation the neutral conjugate base, $[\text{Os}(\text{pap})_2\text{biim}]$, can act as a potential chelating ligand for the synthesis of di- and tri-

metallic complexes. In an attempt to prepare heteropolymetallic Os-Ag system, a methanolic solution of $[\text{Os}(\text{pap})_2\text{biimH}_2]^{2+}$ was stirred with ammoniacal AgNO_3 in 1 : 1 molar proportion at room temperature [eq. (1)].

After 1 h, the resulting brown-violet solution was evaporated slowly at room temperature and the product was isolated as perchlorate salt. X-Ray quality crystals could not be developed after several trials. The compound was characterized based on its analytical data.

Conductance measurement :

The conductivity of the complex in 10^{-3} M methanolic solution is $180 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$, suggesting 1 : 2 electrolytic in nature.

IR spectrum :

The IR spectrum consists of characteristic absorptions^{6,7} for both pap and biim²⁻ ligands. Some selected group frequencies are : (i) a doublet⁸ ($\nu_{\text{N}=\text{N}}$) at ca. 1230 cm^{-1} , (ii) absorption at ca. 1605 cm^{-1} characterizes $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$, (iii) absorption at ca. 750 and 850 cm^{-1} characterizes breathing vibrations^{7b} of the imidazolate rings, (iv) the presence of ionic ClO_4^- was confirmed by the two characteristic absorptions⁹; a broad absorption at 1100 cm^{-1} and a sharp band at 615 cm^{-1} , (v) a broad transition at ca. 3500 cm^{-1} was due to the presence of H_2O as solvent of crystallization. IR spectrum is provided as electronic Supplementary information.

Electronic spectrum :

The visible range absorption spectrum of the complex is dominated by a strong band at 510 nm. The intensity of this transition is almost double¹⁰ of the intensity for the corresponding monomer^{5a}, $[\text{Os}(\text{pap})_2\text{biim}]$. This is an indication of the presence of two numbers of $[\text{Os}(\text{pap})_2\text{biim}]$ moiety in the Os-Ag complex. This lowest energy transition is assigned as MLCT involving $\text{Os}(t_{2g})$ and π^* orbitals of azoimine chromophore. In the UV region, intense absorptions due to superposition of pap and biimidazolate based $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions were observed. The overall spectral pattern of the complex is similar to that of the building unit.

¹H NMR spectrum :

The ¹H NMR spectrum of the compound was recorded in CDCl₃ (Fig. 1). The assignments of pyridyl ring proton signals were made¹¹ on the basis of their chemical shifts and also by examining the spin-spin splitting patterns of the signals. Thus, the signals due to 6-H and 3-H appeared as doublets at δ 8.63 and 7.57 respectively. The triplet resonance appearing at δ 8.12 is assigned to 4-H. The most shielded resonance observed as a double intensity singlet at δ 6.50 which accounts for the presence of two equivalent protons, may be identified^{3b} as the imidazole ring protons (13-H and 15-H). These two protons experienced maximum shielding due to the anisotropic ring current effect of the adjacent pyridine rings of pap ligands. The structure of the compound, under consideration, is shown as an inset in Fig. 1. Due to overlapping of resonances, definitive assignment of the remaining signals was not possible.

ESI mass spectrum :

The ESIMS measurement on [{Os(pap)₂biim}₂Ag₂]²⁺ have been found to be a very strong support in favor of its proposed formulation. Fig. 2 displays the positive ion ESI

mass spectrum¹² of the compound (mol. wt. 1790). The multiply charged ions were generated from loss of negative counter ions, which is denoted by [M-nX]²⁺, where M and X represent the molecule and ClO₄⁻ respectively. The low intensity peak at *ca.* 1690.31 is assigned to [M-X]⁺, which confirms the proposed molecular formula. The peak detected at 796 is due to [M-2X]²⁺ and that at *m/z* 689.15 is due to [Os(pap)₂biimH]⁺, derived from ligand dissociation. The weak peaks at lower *m/z* are of unclear origin and these may be due to fragmentation or unknown combination of fragmented ions.

Fig. 1. ¹H NMR spectrum of the complex in CDCl₃.

Fig. 2. Positive ion ESI mass spectrum of $[\{Os(pap)_2biim\}_2Ag_2](ClO_4)_2$.

Electrochemistry :

The redox responses in both anodic and cathodic regions were determined using cyclic voltammetric studies (Fig. 3). Electrochemical oxidation of the compound leads to decomposition (appearance of a spike at *ca.* 0.15 V)

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of the complex.

and the origin of the irreversible response at 1.05 V is not clear. The cathodic scan however, showed two single-step two-electron reversible reductions at -0.34 V and -0.95 V respectively. The two-electron nature of the reduction has been established by comparing its current height with that of standard ferrocene/ferrocenium couple under identical experimental condition. These responses are assigned to ligand based reductions centered at azoimine chromophore. It is to be noted here that free pap ligand displays two quasireversible voltammetric responses⁶ at -1.31 V and -1.57 V respectively.

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